

Mandelic acid):

In view of the above, it was considered worthwhile to make a detailed study of the oxidation of benzoic acid

Westheimer⁹ type of mechanism could not be operative. The only references available in the literature regarding mechanistic studies of the oxidation of benzoic acid appear to be by P.S. Raman¹⁰ using AgI-dibenzoate and by J. Heran¹¹ using MnO₂. Both have reported benzophenone to be the end product in these reactions. In what follows, a report on the kinetic study of the oxidation of benzoic acid with Ce(IV) has been given.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ceric sulphate was a G.R. product from E. Merck and benzoic acid (m.p. 150°), pure, was from the same source. Other chemicals were either B.D.H. 'Analar' or E. Merck's guaranteed reagents. Solutions of ceric sulphate were prepared¹² in 18 N (1:1) H₂SO₄ and diluted and standardised against ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using *N*-phenylanthranilic acid as indicator. Benzoic acid being slightly soluble in water, a stock solution was prepared by dissolving a weighed quantity of acid in requisite amount of sodium hydroxide solution.

Stoichiometry¹³ was determined by mixing sodium benzoate with 10 to 15 times in molar concentration ceric sulphate solution and leaving the mixture in a constant temperature (30°) bath for several days. It was found that 1 mole of the acid requires 2 moles of ceric sulphate for complete oxidation.

Reactions were carried out at 30.0 ± 0.05° in a thermomix. Reaction was initiated by adding a temperature equilibrated solution of sodium benzoate to a volumetric flask already containing the desired amount of ceric solution, sulphuric acid and water at 30°. Ceric consumption was followed by removing 10 ml aliquots after regular intervals and quenching the reaction by adding it to an excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution. This excess was determined by back titration with standard ceric solution using *N*-phenylanthranilic acid indicator.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Oxidation was initially studied employing stoichiometrically equal concentrations of Ce(IV) and benzilic acid and the reaction was found to be of second order (Fig. 1). The second order constant obtained from the method described above represents the specific rate constant in terms of titre values of ceric sulphate and this depends inversely upon the strength (S) of the titrating solution and directly upon the volume (V) of the reaction mixture titrated. For purpose of comparison specific rate was changed to a standard form K_s by multiplying it by V/S .

TABLE I

Dependence of K_s (in l.g.-equiv.⁻¹min.⁻¹) on H_2SO_4 concentration

Ce (SO₄)₂=.002N; Benzilic acid=.002N; Temp.=30°

H ₂ SO ₄ (N)	K _s	H ₂ SO ₄ (N)	K _s
1.75	159.5	2.75	58.5
2.00	123.0	3.00	48.4
2.25	94.3	3.50	32.85
2.50	72.8	4.00	22.88

On plotting $1/(H_2SO_4)^2$ against K_s (Fig. 2) we get a straight line, as in case of other hydroxy acids⁶ as well as malonic acid⁴.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

TABLE II

Dependence of K_s (in l.g.-equiv.⁻¹min.⁻¹) on hydrogen ion concentration

Ce (SO₄)₂=.002N; Benzilic acid=.002N; Temp.=30°

H ₂ SO ₄	Na ₂ SO ₄	K _s
1.5 N	0.5 N	95.5
1.8 N	0.2 N	104.8
2.0 N	—	123.0

Strength of sulphuric acid was increased in such a way that sulphate ion concentration remains constant, by the addition of sodium sulphate.

Fig. 3 shows that the increase in H_2SO_4 concentration, keeping SO_4^{--} unchanged, increased the rate of reaction.

A study was also made of the influence of a number of alkali sulphates; the values of K_a for the reaction in the presence of 2.0 NH_4SO_4 changed from 123.0 (Na_2SO_4), 75.0 ($NaHSO_4$), 61.0 (K_2SO_4) and 76.2 ($(NH_4)_2SO_4$), when 0.2 N concentration of the above salts was used.

HCl, $NaNO_3$ and NaCl have significant effects only at high concentration of these salts. At 0.25 N concentration of these salts, values of K_a are:

HCl	$NaNO_3$	NaCl
113.1	111.8	99.9

The presence of ClO_4^- increased the rate considerably, presumably $HClO_4$ does not form strong complexes with cerium as is the case with H_2SO_4 , and secondly this might be due to a higher redox potential of ceric ions in this medium.

$MnSO_4$ catalyses the reaction. At 35° the results are:

$MnSO_4$	0	0.0005 M	0.0010 M
K_a	197.5	307.5	463.0

TABLE III

Dependence of K_a on temperature

Ca (SO_4)₂ = 0.002N; Benzoic acid = 0.002N; H_2SO_4 = 2N

Temp $^\circ C$	20	25	30	35
K_a (in l.g. equiv $^{-1}$ min $^{-1}$)	38.93	70.5	123.0	197.5

From above results the values of activation parameters are: $E = 20.28$ K.cal. mole; Entropy = -8.14 cal. at 30° .

TABLE IV

*Dependence of K_1 on the presence of phenyl group in hydroxy acid...*Acid conc. = 0.002N; Ce(SO₄)₂ = 0.002N; H₂SO₄ = 2N; Temp. = 35°

Acid	Glycollic	Mandelic	Benzilic
K_1 (in l.g. equiv ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	6.02×10^{-4}	22.4	197.5

The oxidation of benzilic acid requires two moles of Ce(IV) producing benzophenone which has been isolated from the reaction mixture. The reaction can, therefore, be represented by the following empirical equation:

The mechanism of oxidation by Ce(IV) of various organic compounds has been attributed by different workers^{15,16} to the existence of various complexes in solution in the presence of H₂SO₄:

In addition there will be another equilibrium:

From (2) we can see that an increase of SO₄²⁻ will push the equilibrium towards left giving rise to HSO₄⁻, which in turn would be used in (1) to give rise to more sulphato-cerate complexes which appear to be less reactive. This is in keeping with the results obtained by increasing sulphate ion concentration. However the increase of H₂SO₄ above sulphate ions (Table II) has been found to increase the rate of the reaction, which may be explained on the above basis, reaction (1) being moved to the left; (2) may not be so much disturbed as H₂SO₄ is being increased above SO₄²⁻ ions concentration which is kept constant. Varying values of K_1 with different sulphates can be ascribed to be due to the specific effect of a particular electrolyte on the reaction (2) as pointed out by Shorter and Hinshelwood¹⁵ in their study of the oxidation of acetone by Ce(IV). Electrolytes like NaNO₃, etc. show a much less salt effect, being unable to affect the equilibrium (2) and consequently the equilibrium (1). MnSO₄ catalyses the reaction probably by the oxidation of Mn²⁺ to Mn³⁺ and Mn⁴⁺ as stated by Krishna and Sinha¹⁷ in case of oxidation of thallosion by Ce(IV).

Thus the mechanism appears as follows:

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Evidence for the formation of similar initial chelated species has been reported in detailed studies of complexes of zirconium¹⁸ and thorium¹⁹ ions with hydroxy acids both in aqueous as well as non-aqueous media. Besides this Ce (IV) also reacts with HSO_4^- described in (1) to form more sulphated but less active species of Ce(IV). However all the species of ceric sulphate are in rapid equilibrium and the concentration of the actual active species will be proportional to total amount of Ce(IV) present and hence the rate expression from the above mechanism will be

$$\frac{d\text{Ce(IV)}}{dt} = \frac{k(\text{Benzilic acid})(\text{Ce}^{4+})}{(\text{HSO}_4^-)^2}$$

This mechanism appears to be equally well applicable to the acids of type $\text{HO.CHR}_2\text{COOH}$ and $\text{HO.CR}_2\text{COOH}$. The differing rates of oxidation can be explained on the effect of substituent phenyl groups in facilitating the formation of radical HO.CR_2 (Table V). The values of E and entropy found above (Table IV) also compare well with the values of 16.9Kcal. and 14.0cal/deg. respectively for the hydroxy isobutyric acid reported by Kemp and Waters⁴ who also proposed a similar mechanism for the oxidation of hydroxy acids with one electron oxidants.

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